

FROM SHIPS-TO-CLASSROOMS: EMBEDDING LEADERSHIP STYLES OF MARITIME INSTRUCTORS IN THE ACADEMIC CLASSROOMS

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From Ships-To-Classrooms: Embedding Leadership Styles of Maritime Instructors in the Academic Classrooms

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Abstract

This study investigates the leadership styles of maritime instructors at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College and their impact, focusing on transactional, transformational, and authentic leadership styles. It aims to explore the demographic characteristics of instructors; the leadership styles used onboard ships, the perceived leadership styles in the academic classroom from students' perspectives, barriers to integrating these leadership styles, and the relationship between leadership styles and integration barriers. A descriptive correlational research design was utilized to examine the relationship between instructor demographics, leadership styles, and the challenges of integrating these styles into academic classrooms. Data was collected through a questionnaire administered to maritime instructors and students at the college. The questionnaire includes items on demographics, leadership styles, and perceived barriers. Statistical analysis, including descriptive and inferential statistics, analyzes the data and determines the relationships between variables. The research instruments undergo validation through expert review, pilot testing, and face and content validity considerations. The study's conclusions highlight the leadership styles of maritime instructors, student perceptions, integration barriers, discrepancies between self-assessments and student assessments, and the relationship between leadership styles and barriers. Maritime instructors employ transactional, transformational, and authentic leadership styles, but improvements in communication and addressing certain issues are needed. Students have a positive perception of their instructors, recognizing empowering behaviors. Integration barriers include resistance, training gaps, cultural influences, and policies. Aligning instructors' and students' perceptions is crucial. Increasing the prominence of leadership styles reduces barriers. Recommendations include student engagement, reflection for instructors, investing in training and resources, supporting instructors, advocating for policy changes, and further research. These insights aim to enhance leadership development and education in the maritime industry.

Keywords: *leadership style, transactional, transformational, authentic, maritime, barriers*

Introduction

The shipping industry has witnessed remarkable growth over the past few decades, playing a pivotal role in facilitating global commerce and driving the global economy. However, it is essential to acknowledge that shipping is a sector that spans the globe and carries inherent risks, as highlighted by the International Maritime Organization (Chiu & Lin, 2012; Fuglestedt et al., 2009; Leeuwen & Koppen, 2016). The mission of maritime colleges and universities revolves around the education and development of marine leaders (IMO, n.d.; MARINA, 2019). Considering the increasingly intricate ship systems and the modern marine environment, it has become imperative to equip maritime professionals with advanced teamwork and leadership skills. While the 2010 STCW Manila Amendments emphasize the need for enhanced teamwork and leadership among licensed seafarers (Berkana-Wycoff & Donna, 2014), it is equally crucial to cultivate high leadership and teamwork standards among students pursuing "shoreside" business and policy positions (Berkana-Wycoff & Donna, 2014; Lau & Ng, 2015).

Leadership is not merely an innate quality (Saha & Maji, n.d.; Trevor & Kilduff, 2012; Xhelilaj & Sakaj, 2018) but an art (Allio, 2013; Mea & Carraher, 2015), skill (Maxwell, 2011), discipline (Nicholson, 2013; Xu, 2020), and mindset (Khoza, 2012; Laub et al., 2018) that can be acquired and refined through practice (Kim & Mallam, 2020). In the maritime industry, leadership holds immense significance in ensuring safety (Casareale et al., 2021), security (Paulica et al., 2013), and overall success of maritime operations (Bavlon & Santos, 2019). Within this context, instructors and trainers in the maritime industry play a critical role in shaping future maritime leaders (Kim & Mallam, 2020; Romelczyk & Becker, 2016) by imparting them the essential skills, knowledge, and competencies (Bolaños et al., 2016; Lau & Ng, 2015; Oksavik et al., 2020). Effective leadership within the classroom setting is, therefore, fundamental in preparing future leaders who can effectively navigate the complex and dynamic maritime environment and respond to its challenges and opportunities.

Based on this premise, this study aims to investigate the concept of leadership in the maritime industry, with a particular focus on the perspectives of instructors and trainers. The study will investigate the efficacy of various leadership styles and models utilized in maritime education and training in developing effective leadership skills in future maritime leaders. In addition, the research will analyze the challenges and opportunities associated with classroom leadership and propose adaptive strategies for instructors to achieve sustainable growth and development.

There are numerous leadership styles, each with its effectiveness and repercussions. Future maritime leaders are equipped with frameworks for developing effective leadership skills through applying leadership theories. By incorporating these theories into their instructional strategies, instructors can foster the development of students who can navigate the complex maritime environment and

capitalize on its challenges and opportunities.

One prominent theory is Transformational Leadership, which emphasizes a leader's ability to inspire and motivate followers toward a common goal (Allen et al., 2016; Ellen, 2016; Grant, 2012; H. Khan et al., 2020). Through this theory, maritime professionals can foster a productive workplace and inspire their teams to strive for excellence.

In contrast, transactional leadership emphasizes the significance of rewards and punishments as incentives for followers (Bass & Bass Bernard, 1985; Longshore, 1987). Using this theory, maritime professionals can establish clear performance standards and repercussions for their teams.

Self-awareness and transparency are emphasized in Authentic Leadership theory (Arda et al., 2016). By adopting this methodology, maritime professionals can build trust within their teams by being honest, open, and consistent in their actions and communications.

Through a comprehensive exploration of these leadership styles and theories, this research seeks to contribute to understanding effective leadership in the maritime industry and provide valuable insights for instructors and trainers to enhance their educational practices. By developing future maritime leaders equipped with robust leadership skills, the industry can navigate the challenges and capitalize on the opportunities.

Research Objectives

This study aims to determine the leadership styles, specifically transactional, transformational, and authentic leadership, employed by maritime instructors at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, and to examine their impact. Specifically:

1. To identify maritime instructors' commonly used leadership styles during their onboard ship experiences, focusing on transactional, transformational, and authentic leadership, as assessed by themselves.
2. To assess the commonly used leadership styles of maritime instructors inside the academic classroom, as perceived by the students, with a specific emphasis on transactional, transformational, and authentic leadership.
3. To explore the barriers maritime instructors face in integrating different leadership styles into their teaching, categorizing them as learner, instructor, and environment barriers.
4. To determine if there is a significant difference, compare the leadership styles employed by maritime instructors during their onboard experiences (self-assessed) and in academic classrooms (assessed by students).
5. To determine if there is a significant difference, compare barriers they encounter when integrating leadership styles by maritime instructors during their onboard experiences (self-assessed) and in academic classrooms (assessed by students).
6. To examine the relationship between the leadership styles of maritime instructors and the barriers they encounter when integrating leadership styles.

Literature Review

Maritime Leadership Style

In the maritime industry, the literature identifies various prevalent leadership styles (FjÓrli et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2022; Xhelilaj & Sakaj, 2018). These styles can be classified broadly as transactional (Dhanarajan, 2001; Mara & Mushayi, 2022; Progoulaki et al., 2022), transformational (Agrawal, 2020; CELiK, 2017; Martínez-Moreno et al., 2018; Piwowar-Sulej & Iqbal, 2023), and authentic Leadership (Kleppe & Nortvedt, 2020; Olaniyan & Hystad, 2016; Platenkamp, 2021).

The transactional maritime leadership style is based on a system of rewards and punishments (Bedi et al., 2016; Frangieh & Rusu, 2021). In this leadership style, the leader establishes clear expectations and goals for crew members and then rewards or punishes them based on their performance (Kalsoom et al., 2018). Although transactional leadership can effectively promote accountability and achieve short-term objectives (Tung, 2016), the literature identifies several potential limitations.

A possible limitation of transactional maritime leadership is that it may lead to an emphasis on compliance (Clarke, 2013) rather than creativity (Kim & Lee, 2011) or innovation (Hannah et al., 2020; Sethibe & Steyn, 2018). When crew members are motivated solely by rewards and punishments, they may be less likely to take risks or try new approaches to problem-solving (Chen & Kwak, 2017; Pittig et al., 2014). This can ultimately hinder the organization's capacity to adapt and respond to shifting conditions.

Another possible disadvantage of transactional leadership is that it can foster a culture of mistrust (Chiaburu et al., 2011) and resentment (De Hoogh et al., 2015; Lundell & Marcham, 2018) among crew members (Vealey, 2017). When rewards and punishments are the primary motivation, crew members may feel mistreated or as though their contributions are not valued (Bridoux et al., 2011; Rebitzer & Taylor, 2011; Tremblay et al., 2013). This can result in a decline in job satisfaction, an increase in employee turnover, and a decline in engagement and commitment.

While transformational maritime leadership is a style of leadership that emphasizes inspiring and motivating followers to achieve a shared vision (Gathungu et al., 2015; Grant, 2012; Jiang et al., 2017), transactional maritime leadership is a style of leadership that emphasizes delegating authority (Wahl & Kongsvik, 2017; Xhelilaj & Sakaj, 2018). In this leadership style, the leader focuses on developing the skills, capabilities, and potential of crew members to foster a culture of growth and innovation. Transformational

maritime leadership has several potential benefits, including increased job satisfaction, greater engagement and commitment among crew members, and enhanced performance outcomes (Eliyana et al., 2019; Luu & Phan, 2020; Toban & Sjahrudin, 2016).

Research indicates that transformational leadership can be especially effective in promoting maritime safety and security. Transformational leaders can encourage crew members to take a proactive approach to safety and security (Clarke, 2013; Fernández-Muñiz et al., 2014) rather than simply complying with regulations by fostering a culture of innovation and growth (Jaiswal & Dhar, 2015; Tipu et al., 2012).

However, the literature also notes several potential challenges associated with transformational leadership. A potential obstacle is that it can be difficult to implement, especially in organizations with rigid hierarchies or cultures prioritizing command-and-control Leadership (Banerji & Krishnan, 2000; Credé et al., 2019). Furthermore, transformational leadership requires a high level of emotional intelligence, self-awareness, and empathy from the leader, which can be challenging to develop and maintain (Palmer et al., 2001; Polychroniou, 2009; Wang & Huang, 2009).

In contrast, authentic maritime leadership emphasizes self-awareness, openness, and ethical decision-making (Alexander & Lopez, 2018; Diddams & Chang, 2012). In this leadership style, the leader is open and honest (Hassan & Ahmed, 2011) with crew members about their intentions and values and encourages them to be authentic and true to themselves (Hmieleski et al., 2012). Literature suggests that authentic leadership may benefit the maritime industry, including increased trust, enhanced performance outcomes, and greater crew job satisfaction (Erkutlu & Chafra, 2013; Tabak et al., 2013).

According to research, genuine maritime leaders are more likely to promote a culture of safety and ethics among crew members (Russo et al., 2021; Teperi et al., 2018). By demonstrating ethical decision-making and prioritizing the welfare of crew members, authentic leaders can foster a culture of trust and collaboration, thereby enhancing performance outcomes and preventing safety incidents (N. Khan et al., 2018; Vukonić et al., 2016).

Integration of Maritime Leadership Styles into Academic Classrooms

The integration of maritime leadership styles into academic classrooms has been the subject of several studies in recent years (Baya, 2015; Cheng, 1994; FjØrli et al., 2015; Ng & Yip, 2009; Ubaidillah et al., 2020). Here are some of the key findings from the literature:

Studies have found that leadership development programs can effectively improve students' leadership skills. For example, the study of Wahl & Kongsvik (2018) suggests that crew resource management training in the maritime industry should focus on operationalizing broad concepts such as assertiveness, decision-making, communication, situation awareness, and team coordination while emphasizing the work context and crew-specific needs.

Transformational leadership has been identified as an effective leadership style for the maritime industry. A study by Lu et al. (2016) found that transformational leadership was positively associated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment among seafarers.

Authentic leadership has also been identified as an effective leadership style for the maritime industry (Wahl & Kongsvik, 2018). Studies suggest that authentic leadership positively impacts safety performance among seafarers by promoting positive safety climate perceptions, increasing safety compliance and participation, and influencing safety outcomes through transformational and participative leadership styles (Eid et al., 2012; Gausdal & Makarova, 2017; Hystad et al., 2013).

Several studies have highlighted the importance of experiential learning in leadership development (Bekas, 2015). For example, a study conducted by Zulkifly and Roshamida (2016) and Sellberg & Lundin (2018) found that using simulation technology in the leadership training of naval cadets effectively produces quality graduates to meet the human resources requirement for maritime agencies and industry.

Role of Maritime Instructors

It is impossible to overestimate the impact that maritime teachers will have on the direction the sector takes in the future (Aguado et al., 2015; Heirs & Manuel, 2021; Magramo et al., 2010; Thai et al., 2013; Wahl & Kongsvik, 2018; Yıldırım et al., 2022). Therefore, a review of pertinent studies and literature is necessary to understand the many aspects of their operation.

Multiple studies have highlighted the significance of maritime instructors in providing maritime students with quality education and training. Several studies suggest that the quality of maritime education is determined by instructors' professional and personal development, sense of professional ethics, research, and publication, and effective use of course hours (Aguado et al., 2015; Magramo et al., 2010; Sharma & Nazir, 2021; Yıldırım et al., 2022). Literature highlighted the role of maritime instructors in instilling discipline and work ethic in students, both of which are necessary for a successful maritime career (Wahl & Kongsvik, 2017, 2018).

In addition, several studies have identified maritime instructors' obstacles in performing their duties effectively. Studies found that the lack of resources and support for maritime instructors hinders their capacity to provide high-quality education and training (Alcaide & Llave, 2020; Saray et al., 2021; Thai et al., 2013; Yıldırım et al., 2022). In addition, it highlighted the need for continuous professional development programs to enhance the knowledge and abilities of maritime instructors.

Methodology

This study was designed to investigate the relationship between the demographic profile, leadership styles, and barriers to integrating these leadership styles into the academic classrooms of maritime instructors. Using a descriptive correlational research methodology, a questionnaire was used to gather information from maritime instructors and students at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College.

Students enrolled in the maritime education program and maritime instructors participated in the research. The instructors were selected via stratified random sampling to ensure gender and academic level diversity.

Data were collected in college classrooms where instructors demonstrated their leadership styles and interacted with students. The research instrument was a questionnaire designed by the researcher that covered demographic information, leadership styles, and obstacles. The questionnaire was validated through expert review, content validity, and testing for reliability.

Identifying the target population, obtaining ethical approval, administering the questionnaire, and analyzing the data using descriptive and inferential statistics were all components of the research procedure. Inferential statistics were used to examine relationships and differences among variables, such as correlation analysis, regression analysis, the Mann-Whitney U test, and Spearman's rho.

Results and Discussion

The demographic characteristics of the student and maritime instructor participants in the study provide important insights into the context of the research on the embedding of leadership styles of maritime instructors.

The demographic characteristics of the student participants are presented in Table 1. Most students (43.2 percent) were between the ages of 18 and 21, followed by those between the ages of 21 and 23. (51.8 percent). A lesser proportion (5.0 percent) of students were 26 or older. Male students comprised an overwhelming majority (96.9 percent), while female students constituted only 3.1%. Most students (61.8 percent) were enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation program, while the remaining pursued the Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering program (38.2 percent). 28.0 percent of participants were in their first year, 39.8 percent in their second year, and 32.2 percent in their third year, according to the distribution of participants by year level.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Students

Indicators		Frequency	Percentage
Students Age	18-21 y.o.	165	43.2%
	21-23 y.o.	198	51.8%
	26 y.o. and older	19	5.0%
	Total	382	100.0%
Sex (student)	Female	12	3.1%
	Male	370	96.9%
	Total	382	100.0%
College Program	BSMT	236	61.8%
	BSME	146	38.2%
	Total	382	100.0%
Year Level	1st Year College	107	28.0%
	2nd Year College	152	39.8%
	3rd Year College	123	32.2%
	Total	382	100.0%

*Mean (SD): Age=21 (2)

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of Instructors

Indicators		Frequency	Percentage
Instructors Age	26-35 y.o.	3	27.3%
	36-45 y.o.	2	18.2%
	46-55 y.o.	1	9.1%
	56 y.o. and older	5	45.5%
	Total	11	100.0%
Sex (instructor)	Female	0	0.0%
	Male	11	100.0%
	Total	11	100.0%
Educational Attainment	College Graduate	6	54.5%
	Master's degree (ongoing)	3	27.3%
	Master's degree Graduate	1	9.1%
	Doctorate Degree	1	9.1%
	Total	11	100.0%
Rank	Master Mariner	5	45.5%
	Chief Engineer	1	9.1%
	Second Engineer	3	27.3%

	Third Engineer	2	18.2%
	Total	11	100.0%
Years of experience as a seafarer	1-10 years	3	27.3%
	11-20 years	2	18.2%
	21-30 years	1	9.1%
	31-40 years	5	45.5%
	Total	11	100.0%
Years of experience as a maritime instructor	1-3 years	3	27.3%
	4-6 years	6	54.5%
	7 years and higher	2	18.2%
	Total	11	100.0%

The demographic characteristics of maritime instructors are highlighted in Table 2. The majority of instructors were at least 56 years old (45.5 percent), followed by those between 26 and 35 years old (27.3 percent), 36 to 45 years old (18.2 percent), and 46 to 55 years old (18.2 percent) (9.1 percent). Male instructors comprised the entire sample. 54.5% of instructors held a bachelor's degree, 36.4% were pursuing or had completed a master's degree, and 9.1% held a doctorate. Notably, instructors held specific maritime credentials, such as Master Mariner (45.5%), Chief Engineer (9.1%), Second Engineer (27.3%), or Third Engineer (3%). (18.2 percent). The years of experience as a seafarer varied, with 45.5% having 31-40 years of experience, 27.3% having 1-10 years of experience, 18.2% having 11-20 years of experience, and 9.5% having 21-30 years of experience. 54.5 percent had 4-6 years of experience as maritime instructors, 27.3 percent had 1-3 years of experience, and 18.2 percent had seven or more years of experience.

Table 3 provides an overview of the mean scores, standard deviations (SD), and qualitative interpretations for the three leadership styles: Transactional, Transformational, and Authentic.

Table 3. Descriptive summary of leadership style

Leadership Style	Instructors (Mean SD)	Students (Mean SD)	Descriptive Interpretation
Transactional	3.56 ± 0.63	4.11 ± 0.89	High Agreement
Transformational	3.68 ± 0.59	4.10 ± 0.91	High Agreement
Authentic	3.45 ± 0.60	4.04 ± 0.89	Moderate-High (Instructors), High (Students)

Legend: 1.00-1.50 = very low; 1.51-2.50 = low; 2.51-3.50 = moderately high; 3.51-4.50 = high; 4.51-5.00 = very high

The transactional leadership style was rated highly by both instructors and students. The average score for instructors was 3.56, with a standard deviation of 0.63, while the average score for students was 4.11, with a standard deviation of 0.89. Results suggest that instructors and students agree that transactional leadership is an effective strategy.

Likewise, both instructors and students gave the transformational leadership style high marks. The average score for instructors was 3.68, with a standard deviation of 0.59, while the average score for students was 4.10, with a standard deviation of 0.91. These scores indicate that both groups have a favorable perception of transformational leadership, highlighting its effectiveness in the educational context.

Instructors rated the Authentic leadership style as moderately high, with a mean score of 3.45 and a standard deviation of 0.60, whereas students rated it as high, with a mean score of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.89. Results suggest that instructors perceive Authentic Leadership as slightly more neutral than students, who view it more positively.

Table 3 summarizes the positive ratings that instructors and students have given to the three Transactional, Transformational, and Authentic Leadership styles. Transactional and Transformational styles are consistently rated highly, which demonstrates their effectiveness. While instructors have a more neutral view of Authentic Leadership, students have a more positive view. These findings indicate the presence of positive leadership styles in the academic setting, which fosters an environment conducive to effective leadership and learning.

The difference in leadership styles between students and instructors, as determined by the Mann-Whitney U test, is presented in Table 4. The table provides the mean rank, sum of ranks, Mann-Whitney U statistic, and p-value for each leadership style: Transactional, Transformational, and Authentic.

The Mann-Whitney U test for the Transactional leadership style yielded a p-value less than the significant level of .05 (U=1207.50, p-value=.015), indicating a statistically significant difference between students and instructors. The mean student rank was 199.34, while the mean instructor rank was 115.77. Results suggest that students and instructors perceive Transactional Leadership differently, with students ranking it higher than instructors.

Similarly, the Mann-Whitney U test indicated a statistically significant difference in Transformational leadership style (U=1297.50, p=.028). The average student rank was 199.10, while the average instructor rank was 123.95. This indicates that students have a higher average opinion of transformational leadership than instructors.

Table 4. *Difference in the Leadership Style*

		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>Sum of Ranks</i>	<i>Mann-Whitney U</i>	<i>p-value*</i>
Transactional	Students	382	199.34	76147.50	1207.50	0.015*
	Instructors	11	115.77	1273.50		
	Total	393				
Transformational	Students	382	199.10	76057.50	1297.50	0.028*
	Instructors	11	123.95	1363.50		
	Total	393				
Authentic	Students	382	199.51	76214.50	1140.50	0.009*
	Instructors	11	109.68	1206.50		
	Total	393				

*Difference is significant at the .05 level (2 tailed)

In the case of the Authentic leadership style, the Mann-Whitney U test yielded a p-value less than the .05 significance level (U=1140, p-value=.009), signifying a statistically significant difference. The average student rank was 199.51, while the average instructor rank was 109.68. Results indicate that the perception of Authentic Leadership differs significantly between students and instructors, with students having a higher average rank.

Table 3 summarizes the significant differences between student and faculty perceptions of leadership styles. Students typically rank transactional, transformational, and authentic leadership styles higher than instructors. According to these findings, students and instructors perceive and evaluate different leadership styles in the maritime education context differently. It may be advantageous for instructors to consider these differences and adapt their leadership styles to better align with students' viewpoints, thereby fostering a more positive and effective learning environment.

Table 5. *Descriptive summary of barriers to integrating leadership styles*

<i>Barriers</i>	<i>Instructors</i> (<i>Mean SD</i>)	<i>Students</i> (<i>Mean SD</i>)	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
Learners	2.24 ± 0.75	1.89 ± 0.89	Challenging
Instructors	2.67 ± 0.98	2.12 ± 1.04	Challenging
Environmental	2.27 ± 0.63	1.99 ± 0.93	Challenging

Legend: 1.00-1.50 = extremely challenging; 1.51-2.50 = challenging; 2.51-3.50 = neither challenging nor not challenging; 3.51-4.50 = not challenging; 4.51-5.00 = not at all challenging

The barriers to integrating leadership styles in maritime education are summarized in Table 5. The information is presented in three categories: Learner Obstacles, Instructor Obstacles, and Environmental Obstacles. Each category is characterized by its mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and qualitative description.

Regarding Learner Barriers, the data reveals that learners present a formidable barrier to integrating leadership styles, with instructors having a mean score of 2.24 and a standard deviation of 0.58. Similarly, students perceive learner barriers as complex, with a mean score of 1.89 and a standard deviation of 0.57. The mean of learner barriers is 1.90, indicating that integrating leadership styles is challenging. These findings suggest that integrating leadership styles in maritime education must address significant challenges posed by the characteristics and behaviors of students.

Moving on to Instructor Barriers, the data reveals that instructors face challenging barriers in integrating leadership styles, as indicated by a mean score of 2.67 and a standard deviation of 0.91. With a mean score of 2.12 and a standard deviation of 1.01, students also perceive instructor barriers as challenging. The overall mean for instructor barriers is 2.13, indicating a challenging aspect of integrating leadership styles from the instructor's perspective. These findings suggest that instructors face challenges and obstacles when incorporating different leadership styles into maritime education.

Regarding Environmental Barriers, the data indicates that the environment presents a challenge when integrating leadership styles, with a mean score of 2.27 and a standard deviation of 0.56 among instructors. Similarly, students perceive environmental barriers as difficult, with a mean score of 1.99 and a standard deviation of 0.75. The overall mean for environmental barriers is 1.99, reflecting the environment's challenging nature in terms of integration of leadership style. These results indicate that external factors, such as budget constraints, industry culture, and education policies, impede the implementation of diverse leadership styles in maritime education.

Table 6 presents the analysis results exploring barriers to integrating leadership styles across three domains: Learner, Instructor, and Environment. The table includes the number of participants (N), mean rank, sum of ranks, Mann-Whitney U statistic, and p-value.

There were 382 student participants with a mean rank of 195.37 and a total rank sum of 74632.50 in the Learner domain. The Mann-Whitney U statistic indicates that the difference in barriers to integrating leadership styles between students and instructors in the Learner domain is not statistically significant at the .05 level (U=1479.50, p=.088).

In the Instructor domain, 11 instructors participated, with a mean rank of 253.50 and a total rank sum of 2788.50. The Mann-Whitney U statistic indicates a marginally significant difference in the barriers to integrating leadership styles between students and instructors

in the Instructor domain ($U = 1393.50, p = .053$).

Table 6. *Difference in the Barriers to integrating leadership styles*

Domain		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	p-value*
Learner	Students	382	195.37	74632.50	1479.50	0.088
	Instructors	11	253.50	2788.50		
	Total	393				
Instructor	Students	382	195.15	74546.50	1393.50	0.053
	Instructors	11	261.32	2874.50		
	Total	393				
Environment	Students	382	195.55	74700.50	1547.50	0.129
	Instructors	11	247.32	2720.50		
	Total	393				

*Difference is significant at the .05 level (2 tailed)

In the Environment domain, 382 students participated, achieving a mean rank of 195.55 and a total rank sum of 74700.50. The Mann-Whitney U test indicated that the difference in barriers to integrating leadership styles between students and instructors in the Environment domain was not statistically significant at the .05 level ($U=1547.50, p\text{-value}=.129$).

The results of Table 6 indicate that there may be some differences in the perception of barriers to integrating leadership styles between students and instructors, particularly in the Instructor domain. However, more research is required to fully comprehend the implications of these findings and their significance in the study context.

The Spearman rank correlation analysis presented in Table 10 provides valuable insight into the relationships between leadership styles (Transactional, Transformational, and Authentic) and obstacles encountered by learners, instructors, and the environment. The negative correlation coefficients indicate that barriers diminish as leadership styles become more pronounced. These results illustrate the potential impact of leadership on overcoming obstacles in educational and organizational settings.

Table 7. *Correlation between Leadership Style and Barriers*

		Learners Barriers	instructor Barriers	Environmental Barriers
Transactional	Correlation Coefficient	-.714**	-.602**	-.681**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	393	393	393
Transformational	Correlation Coefficient	-.718**	-.597**	-.687**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	393	393	393
Authentic	Correlation Coefficient	-.725**	-.641**	-.705**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000
	N	393	393	393

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Since the computed p-values are all less than the .05 level of significance, the correlation coefficients reveal significant negative relationships between the Transactional leadership style and all three types of barriers. The significance values (Sig.) of .000 for all correlations indicate that the observed relationships are highly significant, providing substantial evidence of the association between leadership styles and barrier reduction. Results mean that a Transactional leadership style is associated with fewer barriers for learners ($r_s = -.714, p\text{-value} = .000$), instructors ($r_s = -.602, p\text{-value} = .000$), and the environment ($r_s = -.681, p\text{-value} = .000$). The Transformational and Authentic leadership styles exhibit negative correlations with the barriers. These findings suggest that leaders who exhibit Transformational or Authentic behaviors may contribute to creating an environment that is more supportive and barrier-free.

These results suggest that as leaders adopt Transactional, Transformational, or Authentic leadership styles, the obstacles faced by learners, instructors, and the environment will likely diminish. This suggests that particular leadership behaviors and approaches have the potential to create a more supportive and barrier-free environment in educational and organizational settings.

However, it is essential to note that correlation does not imply causation. While these findings highlight the associations between leadership styles and barrier reduction, additional research is required to investigate the underlying mechanisms and establish causality.

In conclusion, the data support the notion that Transactional, Transformational, and Authentic leadership styles are negatively correlated with obstacles encountered by learners, instructors, and the environment. These findings provide organizations and educational institutions valuable insights for addressing barriers and fostering an environment conducive to learning and development. Additional research can expand on these findings and delve deeper into the specific behaviors and strategies associated with each leadership style to inform effective leadership development and practices.

Conclusions

This study investigated the leadership styles of maritime instructors at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College, their impact, and the obstacles encountered when integrating these styles. Students rated Transactional, Transformational, and Authentic leadership styles higher than instructors. The perception of leadership styles by students and professors was found to be significantly different. In learners, instructors, and the environment, obstacles to integrating leadership styles were identified. The study also revealed a significant negative correlation between leadership styles and obstacles, indicating that adopting Transactional, Transformational, or Authentic leadership styles can aid in overcoming obstacles. These findings provide maritime education institutions with insights for promoting effective leadership and overcoming barriers to foster a supportive learning environment. Further research is required to investigate the specific leadership behaviors and strategies associated with each leadership style and establish their causation.

The study recommends implementing a comprehensive leadership development program for instructors in the maritime education program at Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College to improve leadership skills. This program should emphasize transactional, transformational, and genuine leadership styles and equip instructors with the knowledge and skills to integrate them into their teaching practices. In addition, encouraging cross-disciplinary collaboration, organizing workshops and training sessions, fostering a supportive environment, establishing mentorship and coaching programs, promoting research and evaluation, and continually assessing and refining the program are essential for enhancing leadership education in the maritime industry. Implementing these recommendations will result in effective teaching practices and a positive learning environment for instructors and students.

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